

Elliptic Curve Cryptography Encryption Framework for Ensuring Security in Open Social Networks

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Abstract. In today's context, ensuring security in data storage and transfer necessitates the use of data encryption. This study proposes a framework for Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) encryption that ensures data security. In this framework, a graphical user interface has been developed for user interaction. The framework accepts text and image inputs and estimates uploading and downloading times. Only authenticated users are permitted to upload a content and only the authenticated users can download the content. The encryption key is generated which is actually having 128 bits but in this ECC framework, it is truncated to 75 bits. The key generation process is completed in less than 0.5 sec, indicating the efficiency of this approach. The key is considered to be valid in using for encryption or decryption for a maximum time period (40 sec). The ECC algorithm is shown to be highly effective in this framework.

Key words: OSN, Encryption, Cryptography, Elliptic Curve Cryptography, RSA

1. Introduction

In open social networks(OSN) domain, many online platforms like Facebook, Twitter, WhatsApp and many more are available nowadays. As open social networking platforms continue to gain popularity and become an integral part of our daily lives, the need for secure and private communication between users becomes very crucial. One of the big challenges, faced by open social networking platforms, is ensuring secure communication between the users. In order to maintain the security in open social network communication, we are using various cryptographic algorithms. In cryptography, encryption and decryption of data are done by symmetric and asymmetric algorithms. Elliptic curve cryptography (ECC) is a widely accepted and effective method for securing data communication and it is becoming increasingly popular due to its computational efficiency and effectiveness. In recent days, ECC algorithm is successfully implemented in various domains as follows.

An improved version of ECC encryption model is proposed for the IoT sensor data, generates efficient results, when compared with the classical ECC and RSA algorithms[1]. The performance of ECC encryption model, compared with the RSA algorithm is analysed[2]. Group security has been implemented using ECC encryption model and an overview of image encryption using ECC encryption model is discussed [3,4]. Multiple encryption using ECC is analysed with respect to time complexity[5]. Data storage and transfer through cloud network gains prominence for big data applications and the role of ECC algorithm in cloud network is becoming very popular with cryptographic algorithms [6]. The improved version of ECC algorithm and modified AES algorithm is employed for image encryption[7]. The analytical study of hybrid techniques with ECC and AES algorithms for image encryption and decryption has been implemented[8]. In ECC algorithm, the private and public keys are generated during the data transfer process. The genetic algorithm is used along with the ECC algorithm for private key generation and the public key is generated in a random manner. The genetic algorithm coupled ECC encryption/decryption model is found to be proficient in image cryptography and the results are validated in terms of PSNR[9]. Mobile applications play vital role in many real-world scenarios. The ECC algorithm for image encryption in mobile applications is discussed[10].

A comparative analysis of RSA and AES algorithms is discussed and the performance of AES algorithm is found to be better than RSA algorithm. The correlation coefficient value of AES algorithm approaches to zero during encryption that depicts the robust performance [11]. A hybrid encryption model comprising of the ECC algorithm and chaotic map is utilized for image cryptography[12]. The DNA encoding with ECC algorithm is found to be proficient for the image cryptography application [13]. Security of medical images are crucial and the hybrid approach comprising of ECC, linear cryptography and TMIS is found to exhibit excellent security features for these images [14]. The ECC algorithm with multidimensional chaotic maps is implemented for

image cryptography ensuring security in data transfer [15]. The two-stage encryption algorithm, comprising of compressive sensing and ECC, is applied for images. Prior to encryption, the input images are decomposed by wavelet transform and ImproBsys, a novel chaotic system, is used for encryption [16]. A detailed review has been done, focussing on the elliptic curve cryptography for digital image encryption [17]. The group security aspect, utilizing ECC algorithm, is discussed and a classical ECC algorithm along with variant m-gram has been proposed. The ECC m-gram selection algorithm yields proficient results when compared with the classical ECC algorithm [18]. A hybrid combination of chaotic model and ECC algorithm is employed for the encryption of images [19]. The multidimensional hyper-chaotic system and dynamic DNA encoding have been proposed for the encryption of colour images [20]. An enhanced multiple session key (EMSK) protocol relies on ECC algorithm for text and image encryption [21].

The elliptical curve pseudo random number and chaotic random number sequence have been used for the encryption of images for e-governance applications [22]. A lightweight encryption scheme, based on ECC, is utilized for secure data communication between IoT devices in smart home [23]. The hybrid approach comprising of AES and ECC cryptographic algorithms has been deployed for secure sharing of text and images [24]. An efficient hardware implementation of ECC processor over prime field has been resulted in optimized resource sharing mechanism which leads to reduction in area and less energy consumption [25].

In our study we use ECC algorithm to develop a framework which ensures the security of data transfer in open social networks. This paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides a detailed discussion of Elliptic curve cryptography. The performance of the proposed method, which includes the authentication of owners, uploading of text and images from the owner's side, private key generation, time analysis for secret key generation, authentication for receivers, downloading of images from the receiver's side and encrypted key generation for various types of text and image files are presented in section 3. In this study, text in doc/docx, PDF and rich text format as well as images in tiff, jpg, png and bmp formats have been used as data, described in section 3. We highlight the conclusions in section 4.

2. Details of Elliptic Curve Cryptography Algorithm

2.1 Basics of Elliptic Curves

This study proposes elliptic curve cryptography encryption model for the data transfer in open social networks. In ECC, asymmetric encryption strategy is used where private key is utilized for encryption of data and public key is used for decryption of data. The asymmetric encryption is depicted below in Fig.1.

Fig.1. ECC encryption model

The elliptic curve cryptography is derived from the elliptic curves in mathematics. The elliptic curves are the algebraic curves which comprises of the coordinates x and y as given in the Eq.(1).

$$\boxed{Ax^3+Bx^2y+Cxy^2+Dy^3+Ex^2+Fxy+Gy^2+Hx+Iy+J=0} \quad \text{---(1)}$$

The cryptography utilizes elliptic curves in a simplified form (Weierstrass form), given in the Eq.(2).

$$y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \quad \text{---(2)}$$

The ECDH (Elliptic Curve Diffie–Hellman) key exchange scheme is used to generate a shared secret key. The shared secret key is used for encryption and decryption of data.

The encryption process is summarized as follows:

Consider a cryptographic elliptic curve in a finite field with a generator point G.

Estimation Encryption Key (public Key) --> (Shared ECC Key, cipher text Public Key)

Formulate cipher text Private Key = *new random private key*.

Estimate cipher text Public Key = cipher text Private Key * G.

Estimate the ECDH shared secret key: Shared ECC Key = Public Key * cipher text Private Key.

The shared ECC Key and cipher text Public Key are estimated and utilized in this work. The shared ECC Key is utilized for symmetric encryption. The randomly generated cipher text Public Key is used to calculate the decryption key.

The decryption process is summarized as follows:

Estimation Decryption Key (Private Key, cipher text Public Key) --> shared ECC Key

Estimate ECDH shared secret: shared ECC Key = cipher text Public Key * private Key.

Return the shared ECC Key and use it for the decryption.

The concept of elliptic curve cryptography is explained with the help of the example as follows. Let Owner (A) and Receiver (B) be two nodes involved in communication. The QA and dA represent the public key and private key generated by Owner. The QB and dB represent the public key and private key generated by Receiver, public keys are exchanged between the nodes. The shared key is represented as $dA \times dB \times G$. G represents the generator point on the elliptic curve.

The public and private keys are generated by the Receiver taking into account of a point on the curve. The public key of the Receiver with respect to the private key is calculated using Eq.(3).

$$QB = dB \times G \quad \text{---(3)}$$

In similar manner, the public and private keys of the Owner are generated. The public key of the Owner with respect to the private key is calculated using Eq.(4).

$$QA = dA \times G \quad \text{---(4)}$$

Key exchange between the nodes is the next phase where Owner and Receiver utilize the public and private keys to estimate the shared key. The shared key of Owner is given in Eq.(5).

$$\text{Shared key of Owner} = dA \times QB = dA \times dB \times G \quad \text{---(5)}$$

The Receiver will utilize the Owner's public key and private key to estimate the shared key as given in Eq.(6).

$$\text{Shared key of Receiver} = dB \times QA = dB \times dA \times G \quad \text{---(6)}$$

The performance of the ECC is found to be proficient when it is compared with other classical encryption algorithms like RSA, AES, DES etc.

The privacy and security issues, related to Open Social Networks are crucial, and this study paves way towards the efficient transfer of data through ECC algorithm. Users (Owners) directly manage access control to the photos via shared keys that are independent of online social networks or other third parties. It is guaranteed that only the recipient with the right credentials retrieves the original data.

The implementation of the proposed ECC framework is as follows:

The owner is authorized by login credentials.

Uploads (viz. texts and images) are done by the authorized users.

Only after authenticating (i.e., accepting receiver's request), a public key is generated and it is shared with the receiver to view the text /image.

Shared keys expires automatically after specified time to avoid sharing of the keys with others.

Every time, any user, other than the owner wants to view the data uploaded, needs to be authorized by the owner.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Key generation on Owner side

Elliptic curve cryptography is an asymmetric encryption method that uses elliptic curves to generate a pair of keys: a public key and a private key. The security of ECC is based on the difficulty of calculating the discrete logarithm of a random elliptic curve. This means that the private key cannot

be easily determined from the public key, making it an excellent method for securing data communication. To implement ECC for securing communication on an open social networks, we must first generate the public and private keys for each user. This can be done using an elliptic curve generator that generates a unique elliptic curve for each user.

Once the elliptic curve is generated, the public key can be calculated by multiplying the curve generator by a random number. The private key is then generated by multiplying the elliptic curve generator by a secret integer (shared key), known only to the user.

Once the public and private keys are generated using ECC, then the communication between users can be secured. When a user wants to send a message to another user, they encrypt the message using the owner's public key. The receiver can then decrypt the message using their private key, ensuring that only the intended recipient can read the message. The cryptography framework has been developed in Javascript and executed in the system with the following specifications.

A graphical user interface is developed with Eclipse IDE in this study and it facilitates the users to interact with this ECC framework. The authenticated users (owners) are given rights to upload the contents and the contents may be images as given in Table.1. and text files as given in Table.2.

Table.1.Details of the images, uploaded by the users (Owners)

Filename	Type	Size	Timestamp	Upload time in ms	User ID
bird.tiff	tiff	65,666.00	2022-07-30 06:21:46	1.26	O1
frymire.tiff	tiff	3,706,306.00	2022-07-30 08:05:39	2.89	O2
monarch.tiff	tiff	1,179,784.00	2022-07-30 08:01:43.0	2.65	O3
nature.bmp	bmp	53,747,85.00	2022-03-30 19:54:59.0	3.07	O4
sky.bmp	bmp	14,749,696.00	2022-05-29 07:04:55.0	2.87	O5
corona1.jpg	jpeg	588955.00	2022-07-30 08:01:43	1.19	O6
sat2.jpg	jpeg	99,255.00	2022-07-30 08:05:07	1.78	O7
eva.jpg	jpeg	198,891.00	2022-07-30 08:02:09	1.04	O8
centos.png	png	62,229.00	2022-07-30 08:04:22	1.24	O9
feather.png	png	1,313,888.00	2022-07-30 08:03:26	2.33	O10

Table.2.Details of text files, uploaded by the users (Owners)

Filename	Type	Size	Timestamp	Uploaded Time in ms	User ID
c4611_sample_explain-pdf.pdf	PDF	88226.00	2022-08-03 20:09:43.0	0.97	O1
file-sample_1MB-rtf.rtf	Rich Text Document	1033645.00	2022-08-03 20:10:12.0	1.76	O2
file-sample_500kB-rtf.rtf	Rich Text Document	502695.00	2022-08-03 20:10:25.0	1.32	O3
quod-txt.txt	Text Document	2859.00	2022-08-03 20:11:09.0	0.52	O4
runfile-doc.doc	DOC File	26069.00	2022-08-03 20:11:34.0	0.63	O5
textcollector-txt.txt	Text Document	1183.00	2022-08-03 20:11:48.0	0.47	O6
usedbook-docx.docx	Office Open XML Document	11534.00	2022-08-03 20:12:02.0	0.56	O7
word-training-docx.docx	Office Open XML Document	5,516,086.00	2022-08-03 20:12:15.0	1.11	O8
dictionary.pdf	PDF	1233645.00	2022-08-03 21:16:27.0	1.92	O9
lorem-rtf.rtf	Rich Text Document	402695.00	2022-08-03 21:16:41.0	1.24	O10

Table.1. shows the details of image files, uploaded by the users and it comprises of tiff, jpeg, bmp and png files. The time taken for uploading relies on the size of file and the processor specifications.

Table.2. shows the details of text files, uploaded by the users and it comprises of pdf, txt, doc, docx and rtf files. The time taken for uploading relies on the size of file and the processor specifications.

The ECDH algorithm offers two users to find a shared secret key and get in touch over an insecure communication channel. This algorithm works with a key pair, public key and private key concept. It allows two users to share a secret key to provide secure communication through the channel. These security solutions are deployed in ensuring user authentication and integrity of data. The security of the ECDH key exchange relies on the difficulty of computing the private key from the public key, which is believed to be a hard problem in elliptic curve cryptography. Therefore, an eavesdropper who intrudes the public keys exchanged between owner and receiver cannot determine the shared secret key easily.

Computing the public key:

To compute owner's public key, point multiplication is performed by selecting a base point G on the elliptic curve.

Table.3. shows the secret key, generated for ensuring authentication to the users. In this table, the first column shows the user ID of Owners, second column shows the secret key generated and third column shows the time taken (in ms) for key generation.

Table.3. Secret key generated for the Owners

Owner ID	Secret key Generated	Time taken for key Generation (in ms)
O1	ZCD3511438	0.202
O2	ZCD3511438	0.194
O3	XCA9327884	0.211
O4	LJD6078886	0.186
O5	ZCQ9573115	0.190
O6	ZCD3511438	0.213
O7	EIX9587304	0.216
O8	ZGZ9348156	0.205
O9	ZZK9317228	0.197
O10	LDI06776603	0.172

3.2.Key Generation on Receiver side

Private Key Generation:

Each node generates a private key in which owner chooses a random integer **a** and receiver chooses a random integer **b**. These integers are kept secret.

Public Key Generation:

Each node computes their public key by multiplying the base point **G** by their private key as explained here. Owner computes $A = aG$ and Receiver computes $B = bG$.

Exchange Public Keys:

Owner and Receiver exchange their public keys over the insecure communication channel.

Shared Secret Key Calculation:

Owner and Receiver can now compute a shared secret key. Owner computes $S = aB = a(bG) = (ab)G$. Receiver computes $S = bA = b(aG) = (ab)G$. Since $(ab)G$ is the same point for both parties, they now share a secret key. Table.4. displays the details of secret key generated and time taken for key generation on the Receiver side. It shows the key generated after authentication by the owner for the receiver to download the file. Table.5. shows the downloading phase details of images after the successful generation of keys on the receiver side.

Table.4. Secret key generated for the Receivers

Receiver ID	Secret key	Time taken for key generation (in ms)
R1	IOA8527299	0.166
R2	DDZ1805084	0.194
R3	HKB8155164	0.218
R4	TZB9179154	0.163
R5	ZMQ6471204	0.158
R6	RDZ5807868	0.149
R7	RJM5448867	0.172
R8	ZSB3521483	0.204
R9	IDB6785946	0.162
R10	DAI4077245	0.183

Table.5. Downloading phase details of images.

FileName	Receiver ID	Download time in ms	Timestamp
bird.tiff	R1	1.16	2022-07-30 07:15:42
frymire.tiff	R2	2.43	2022-07-30 08:16:25
monarch.tiff	R3	2.26	2022-07-30 09:11:43
nature.bmp	R4	2.96	2022-03-30 08:42:45
sky.bmp	R5	2.58	2022-05-29 08:14:55
coronal.jpg	R6	1.07	2022-07-30 09:33:23
sat2.jpg	R7	1.39	2022-07-30 09:15:27
eva.jpg	R8	0.09	2022-07-30 09:22:19
centos.png	R9	1.12	2022-07-30 09:25:37
feather.png	R10	2.06	2022-07-30 10:13:46

3.3.Expiration Time for Keys

A timer is kept to keep track of the key generation and its expiry. In our study, the key expires after 40secs. If the receiver fails to copy the generated keys, he needs to raise a request again and the owner has to authenticate the request to download the data . This time tracking feature ensures data security by not allowing the receiver to share the key with third person.

Adding a timestamp:

When the key is generated, a timestamp is added to the key metadata, indicating the date and time when the key is created. This is stored in a separate database.

Checking the timestamp:

When the key is used, the timestamp is checked against the current time of the system to determine whether the key has expired. The key is considered to be valid in using for encryption or decryption for a maximum time period (40 sec).

3.4.Encryption of Data during communication

Table.6. displays the details of encryption key generated corresponding to the image files in which the key length does not exceed 75 bits. Table.7. displays the encryption key generated with respect to the text files and the key length does not exceed 75 bits. This indicates the efficiency of ECC encryption algorithm.

Table.6. Encryption of data, corresponding to the image files

Filename	Encrypted Key
bird.tiff	kDqLBkZ6+UKZR0EdYubjYQ2V5Y19TJFYl3te/p34gz8wzxf/VftP9hbv3rOlwyj
frymire.tiff	NcNXp1KLWdUmH9eE7rW0vTf5BK+drCBPXs6OA0qWb7H1SggEYA+GZWxeVNbJ0i6V
monarch.tiff	z3wB/Gi18HwtZQ341ZYhZxDXuYwaaPiRLRM5mCojW7QITR+yJFHBnTMxkKw020ky
nature.bmp	uxFlnjS+378s9iM4tKwtpLB/yH1rE+SftEvNmWFiAi+vij1MAI/dyOiiFRovi7Qr07XMqJ9Myic=
sky.bmp	z3wB/Gi18HwtZQ34MqJ9/p34gz8+drCBPXdsaq26GTRc/oLIu6-ghqxcvNDWecvbu=L0y
corona1.jpg	Acfr761JHnercx+WXcty0/MsQW197gz6cjr=O0pn21FRbcxZ3VftP9hbv3rWQsdyfirt=21j
sat2.jpg	vXZawplj652+cvbbVpuji7Bmytt90vcgoAsFGH63=3rOlwyjMdrHp=+Vqsdf5h/qmnDsftr+w
eva.jpg	svuy67Mncx+2VbnmuTrES/mj=eExASrte42=HMnoljde49nm16fdSEwaqoXcvtusM714Xz
centos.png	ZAncrTuJ219vdef00fdsxgx+sfacdsfLdpRew/mnfDEpom+wQoVxzsiUP973aXZurcleYt
feather.png	cdERmUi921vbseTYnvDes=mjdsszM/xer218pEomAcD+csnbnuiLvcxdQlomnxs+2c19B

Table.7. Encryption of data, corresponding to the text files

Filename	Encrypted Key
c4611_sample_explain-pdf.pdf	Vmjutes2189ndxey=jhgdxzUO06hjkKIHCgti/esaRmnrePwx+cxsZxAS76jusdaq+FGvm
file-sample_1MB-rtf.rtf	nmmnfDEpojut+65XZvce2/mIO019sztrfdGLMbveridvtdn=fsifnpuYVcdtrv1c8c0M=dx
file-sample_500kB-rtf.rtf	Ovcdsir65csehyfr+hjedfdumypDSew/jyvfd54vcx6aprbmFPSmcivc/mlo+=AHuewqm7dFr
quod-txt.txt	nciytdYP5fcj-njcds/vfFbdqXZ09+bbTuIO8oXprWqnm=/cQWpmdytrv6233hjKcewQ1=ltr
runfile-doc.doc	sPygvb098/w2awytvgni+-vg/QBnyudh54B3bhui+buvvNMwexz=kuts+daxdfPI0iwMd19HiqS
textcollector-txt.txt	Cviufpo+gtd4/vcfZpOIgqRexc09mxcR56hq+=xsftsr-/dxzHqPOImnfzxd+=cxes/ cfrt26hgf
usedbook-docx.docx	m8nyrc9PQxsvijft6nj/hjt=gfasLZvcyutygd810ber3/u+c3a/+VXaqpoin6xreCUi09Mqsh
word-training-docx.docx	Slytfr8fdx+-z/dFWeqmcxdoUt65Cvnoiu=iJ/XQmohyu64vtf3+lkh/creAlkMnUIIdR-nm+/ds2n
dictionary.pdf	csIou87bCxzr+iio=1nm8dx0vcVseRVCgfv/+nnj-jiyfd/Xwq2bfd9VR8mdpo0iDver+4c
lorem-rtf.rtf	Xzw56lkj=/ijJIEcbvytd+fdstryurd+/fesa21987sdyu3LsdcfYu=fds/C33bf6rV+/wa-fcx/fdsDQw6n/k

Decrypting the messages:

To decrypt messages sent by owner, receiver uses private key to perform point multiplication on owner's ciphertext. This allows receiver to recover the original data.

Using ECC on an open social network has several benefits. Firstly, it provides a high level of security and privacy for communication between users. Secondly, it is computationally efficient, meaning that it does not require a significant amount of computing power to secure data communication. This is important for open social networking platforms as they may have millions of users communicating with each other simultaneously. Finally, ECC is widely accepted and standardized, making it a reliable method for secure data communication.

4. Conclusions

This study proposes ECC encryption framework for ensuring data security in Open Social Networks and the privacy of the data is sustained. The text and image inputs are utilized in this study for secure data transmission and the performance of the ECC encryption framework is found to be efficient. The authentic users are only

eligible to upload the data and for those who have authentication rights from the owner are only eligible to download the uploaded contents within a specified time after which the key expires automatically. The key generation time is found to be very less and the downloading time relies on the size of the data. The graphical user interface which has been developed for implementing ECC Encryption Framework enables the users to interact in an efficient manner. By implementing ECC, open social networking platforms can provide their users with a secure and private communication environment, building trust and increasing user satisfaction.

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